

SITE CHARACTERIZATION REPORT

IV.HSRS: Siracusa (SR)

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3. Active seismic measurements and processing

The active seismic line was deployed approximately 10 m from the station HSRS, along a ENE-WSW direction (Fig. 2). For the sake of a comprehensive subsurface characterization, Multichannel Analysis of Surface Waves (MASW; Park et al., 1999) was conducted.

Fig. 2 Satellite view of the study area and acquisition layout. Green triangle: HSRS seismic station; red triangles: MASW array; red stars shot points; blue triangles: single station measurement points.

3.1 Equipment

To conduct the site characterization, we used a set of 25 three-component geophones (4.5 Hz corner frequency). The geophones set was connected to a SoilSpy Rosina datalogger. An 8-kg sledgehammer hitting a flat metal plate was used as seismic source at two shot locations (red stars in Fig. 2) positioned outside the geophone line. The synchronization between the traces recorded by the geophones and the seismic source was ensured by the first geophone-trigger.

3.2 Geometry of the acquisition array

The 25 vertical-component receivers were deployed at regular intervals of 3 m (Fig. 3), resulting in a total length of 72 m. The geophones were installed using metal spikes inserted into the ground to ensure proper soil coupling (Fig.3). The MASW survey was performed placing the sources at the two ends of the deployment 10 m distant from the last geophone (red stars in Fig. 2). At these shooting positions the sledgehammer was vertically blown on a flat metal plate for Rayleigh wave generation.

Fig. 3 Geophone array in place. The picture was taken near the eastern end of the line (viewpoint W to E).

3.3 Acquisition

In Fig. 4 we show a representative seismic section obtained from a hammer shot. The acquisition parameters adopted for MASW was the following: sampling frequency = 256 Hz, record length = 3 s, pre-trigger delay = -0.6 s. At the source points, 6 hammer shots were blown and the traces generated were saved in separated .sg2 file (without automatic stack).

Fig. 4 Examples of acquired seismic sections from vertical component wave shot.

3.4 Processing

3.4.1 Rayleigh wave data $f-k$ processing

Rayleigh wave dispersion characteristics were extracted from the vertical component seismograms from MASW survey. The achieved seismic records were processed by using $f-k$ (frequency – wavenumber) transform (Kvaerna and Ringdahl, 1986), to obtain a conversion of the recorded sets of traces from time–offset to frequency–wavenumber domain and then Rayleigh waves dispersion curves. To improve the Signal-to-Ratio (S/N), the Rayleigh wave dispersion curve panels from single shot records with the same source position were summed produced staked spectral images (O’Neill, 2003; Neducza, 2007). The energy maxima of the

Rayleigh wave dispersion curves were picked on these stacked panels; spectral amplitude peaks from individual shot records were identified and used to define the uncertainty intervals in the estimation of phase velocities (Socco et al., 2009; Boiero and Socco, 2010). Fig. 5 shows the dispersion curves obtained from the considered seismic records together with the stacked dispersion curve derived from the forward and reverse acquisitions, as well as the corresponding picked energy maxima. The dominant feature observed in both spectra considering the shot at the eastern and western ends of the line is a branch extending continuously in the 14.0-40.0 Hz frequency band. This feature is interpreted as superimposition of Rayleigh wave modes.

Fig. 5 Phase velocity versus frequency stacked spectra obtained considering the recordings from the two shot points at the E and W ends of the deployments and the total stacked curves.

4. Passive seismic measurements

4.1 Acquisition and equipment

In addition to the active seismic survey, five single-station noise recording measurements were performed on the same acquisition day (Blue triangle in Fig. 2). The sensors (SmartSolo IGUDB3C-5 seismometer) were partially buried in the ground to improve coupling with the soil (Fig. 6). The sampling frequency was 200 Hz, and the recordings spanned a 40-minute time interval.

Fig. 6 Single-station IGUDB3C-5 ambient vibration recording.

4.2 Single station processing

The ambient vibration recordings were processed with the aim of:

- estimate the H/V ratio of recorded noise, thus identifying the resonance frequency of the site (Nakamura, 1989) using classical H/V methods (as implemented in Geopsy software (www.geopsy.org; Wathelet et al., 2020)).

The results of the different measurements points show a generally consistent spectral ratio curve, indicating limited lateral variability in the investigated area (Fig. 7).

The HVSR curves exhibit a relatively flat curve over most of the investigated frequency range, consistent with stiff subsurface conditions. A slight amplitude increase is observed towards the high frequency with a slight peak at about 12.6 Hz. This high-frequency peak (not significant) may be related to shallow velocity contrasts or superficial deposits present in the area.

Fig. 7 H/V ratio versus frequency obtained from the processing of noise recording data.

5 Inversion of surface wave data

The Rayleigh wave dispersion curves obtained from the processing of active seismic data were inverted for the 1D S-wave velocity profile of the investigated site. For the inversion the *dinver* code implemented in Geopsy (Wathelet et al., 2020) was used. The code provides a set of V_s models compatible with the observed dispersion curve. This inversion tool uses a directed-search method, called “neighbourhood algorithm” (Sambridge, 1999).

5.1 Inversion target

The inversion target (Fig. 8) consists of:

- The Rayleigh wave dispersion curve, as obtained from the processing of active data with the $f-k$ processing. The forward and reverse shot dispersion curves showed good agreement; therefore, a stacked dispersion curve combining both directions was adopted for the analysis to improve the frequency range coverage.
- Two modes were identified and used in the inversion.

5.2 Parameterization of the model space

For the parameterization of the subsurface model, the soil column was represented as a stack of four homogeneous layers overlying a half-space. Within each layer, V_s values were allowed to vary within broad boundaries (50–3500 m/s).

5.3 Inversion results

We performed the inversions using the Dinver routine (<http://www.geopsy.org/>). The inversion run produced 100000 total models in order to assure a good exploration and exploitation of the parameter space. The result of the inversion is shown in Fig 8. The 4-layer parametrization yields low misfit values 0.0039, with the velocity profiles generally consistent.

Fig. 8 Dispersion curves for the Rayleigh waves and S-wave velocity profiles. The red line indicates the best-fitting model.

6. Interpretation of the velocity profiles

6.1 Velocity profiles

The inverted V_s profile (Fig. 8) reveals a progressive increase in shear-wave velocity with depth, ranging from ~ 500 – 700 m/s in the shallowest layers to ~ 1600 – 1800 m/s below ~ 10 – 15 m depth. The derived V_{S30} value of 1086 ± 14 m/s indicates stiff rock conditions and the site can be classified as soil class A according to both Eurocode 8 (EC8) and NTC 2018.

A marked velocity contrast is observed at depths of approximately 10–15 m, which may correspond to the slight resonance peak identified in the HVSr analysis. The overall velocity structure is consistent with the relatively flat HVSr response, and the limited amplification observed at the site.

7. Discussion and conclusions

The HVSR analysis at the HSRS station shows a generally flat spectral response with limited increase in amplitude at high frequency, consistent with stiff ground conditions. A weak resonance peak is observed at high frequency, suggesting the presence of a shallow impedance contrast.

The inversion of the active seismic measurements provided a V_s profile characterized by a progressive increase in shear-wave velocity with depth. Near-surface layers exhibit V_s values of approximately 500–700 m/s, while velocities increase up to ~1600–2000 m/s below ~10–15 m depth, indicating the presence of stiff geological formations.

The derived V_{S30} value of 1086 m/s classifies the site as EC8 class A, confirming very stiff subsurface conditions. The observed velocity contrast is consistent with the weak high-frequency resonance identified by the HVSR analysis.

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